

Rotation-powered pulsars in the soft- and medium energy gamma-ray bands

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on behalf of a larger collaboration

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Five classes/manifestations of neutron star systems:

- accretion powered (gravitational energy; binary systems LMXBs/HMXBs)
- spin-down powered (rotation energy loss; RPP)
- magnetically powered (decay magnetic field; magnetar)
- thermal emitters (XDINS)
- wind-wind interaction binaries

End product of stellar evolution:

Collapsed core of 10-25 M_{\odot} massive supergiant star

Ultra-compact: $\sim 1.4 M_{\odot}$
radius : $\sim 10-12$ km!

Rapidly spinning ($P \sim 1.7$ ms - 30 s or even more?)
objects with magnetic fields strengths of about 10^{8-15} Gauss

Particle acceleration in magnetosphere \rightarrow X-rays, γ -rays

Lighthouse model \rightarrow Pulsar!

Heritage

CGRO: 5 April 1991 - 4 June 2000
(20 keV - 30 GeV)

Only 4 pulsars detected in hard X-ray regime (>20 keV)....

1) Classical γ -ray pulsars
(>100 MeV; SAS-2, COS-B
during seventies, eighties)

PSR B0531+21 (Crab)
PSR B0833-45 (Vela)

2) Newly discovered **high-energy**
 γ -ray pulsars (>30 MeV)

PSR B1706-44
PSR B1055-52
PSR B1951+32
Geminga

PSR J0218+4232, ms-pulsar!

PSR B0656+14

PSR B1046-58

3) Newly discovered **soft** γ -ray
pulsars (20 keV $< E < 30$ MeV)

PSR B1509-58

PSR B0540-69 (RXTE HEXTE)

(de Plaa, Kuiper, Hermsen 2003)

Soft/medium γ -rays pulsars: $20 \text{ keV} < E_\gamma < 30 \text{ MeV}$
 (Compton dominated regime - 'MeV' gap)

Spacecrafts with hard X-ray / gamma-ray instruments

NICER (June 2017+)

Dedicated X-ray timing mission

- 0.2 - 12 keV
- Abs. Timing < 100 ns
- FoV 30 arcmin²
- Concentrator optics (56x); NO imaging; high-sensitive area!

Soft γ -rays pulsars: 18 secure members in catalogue

name	Kuiper & Hermsen 2015 MNRAS 449, 3827	period (ms)	age (kyr)	$^{10} \log(L_{sd})$	radio	pulse shape	photon index	<i>Fermi</i> LAT/Pulsed	TeV PWN/Pulsed
PSR J0205+6449 (3C58)		65.7	5.4	37.43	very dim	two sharp pulses	-1.1(1)	yes	yes
PSR J0534+2200 (Crab)		33.5	1.23	38.66	bright	two pulses	curved	yes	yes/yes
PSR J0537-6910 (N157B in LMC)		16.1	4.9	38.69	quiet	single, sharp	-1.57(1)	no	yes
PSR J0540-6919 (N158A in LMC)		50.5	1.7	38.18	very dim	structured broad	curved	no	...
PSR J0835-4510 (Vela)		89	11	36.84	bright	multiple sharp	-1.1	yes	yes/yes
PSR J1400-6325 (IGR J14003-6326)		31.2	12.7	37.71	dim	single, broad	-1.95(4)	no	no
PSR J1513-5908 (MSH 15-52)		150	1.6	37.26	bright	single broad	curved	yes	yes
PSR J1617-5055		69.0	8.0	37.20	very dim	single, broad	-1.42(2)	no	?
PSR J1640-4631 (G338.3-0.0)		206	3.4	36.64	quiet	single	-1.3	no	yes
PSR J1811-1925 (G11.2-0.3)		65.0	24.0	36.81	quiet	single, broad	-1.11(1)	no	no
PSR J1813-1246		48.1	43.0	36.80	quiet	two pulses	-0.85(3)	yes	...
PSR J1813-1749 (G12.82-0.02)		44.7	5.6	37.75	quiet	single, broad	-1.30(3)	no	yes
PSR J1838-0655 (AX J1838.0-0655)		70.5	23.0	36.75	quiet	structured broad	-1.12(1)	no	yes
PSR J1846-0258 (Kes 75)		324	0.72	36.91	quiet	single, broad	-1.20(1)	no	yes
PSR J1849-0001 (IGR J18490-0000)		38.5	42.8	36.99	quiet	single, broad	-1.37(1)	no	yes
PSR J1930+1852 (G54.1+0.3)		136	2.9	37.08	very dim	single, broad	-1.21(1)	no	yes
PSR J2022+3842 (G76.9+1.0)		48.6	8.9	37.47	very dim	two sharp pulses	-1.20(2)	no	no
PSR J2229+6114 (G106.6+2.9)		51.6	10.5	37.34	weak	two pulses	-1.11(3)	yes	yes

Kuiper & Hermsen
2015

Soft gamma-ray pulsar population spectral characteristics: νF_ν peaks at MeV energies (LAT population at GeV energies)

Question: Are there more 1509-58 like pulsars with detectable soft & high-energy gamma-ray emission (>30 MeV)?

AX J1838.0-0655	no radio...		
IGR J1849.0-0000	no radio...		
PSR J1846-0258	no radio...	timed at X-rays!	PCA (<2012), Swift XRT (2011.5-2018)

PSR J1846-0258 indeed soft γ -ray pulsar (8 yr LAT timing)!

Motivated by this result:

- In March 2017 Swift-XRT (WT) monitoring of AX J1838.0-0655 started , as well as we had a long obs. (14 ks) on IGR J18490-0000
- Monitoring for all three pulsars continued by NICER in 2018+ through accepted proposals (PSR 1846-0258 & AX J1838.0-0655) and via legacy program (IGR J18490-0000)

Geometries of high-energy emission pulsar models

Strategy for soft γ -ray detection of pulsed emission in 'MeV' gap (~ 0.3 -30 MeV)

- Create timing model (ephemeris) from radio-, X-ray- or HE gamma-ray observations

1) Radio: e.g. Crab pulsar (JBO monthly ephemerides)

2) X-rays: radio quiet/weak pulsars : PSR J1846-0258, AX J1838.0-0655,
NICER (RXTE-PCA in the past) IGR J18490-0000, PSR J2022+3842, ...

3) gamma-rays (>100 MeV) :

PSR B0833-45 (=Vela),
PSR J1813-1246

(for both also NICER monitoring could do the job)

- Pulse-phase folding technique:

determine pulse phase, remove integer part and STACK

INTEGRAL contribution to RPP research (<300 keV) : 2002 - 2022

- Detailed Crab (pulsar) studies due to its brightness
 - a) polarisation measurements IBIS / SPI
 - b) phase resolved spectra ISGRI
 - c) dynamics of PWN, variations in Crab flux, **not** standard candle!
 - d) Crab pulsar as inflight calibration source for absolute timing: soft γ -rays $-248 \mu\text{s}$ earlier than radio pulse
Established consistent timing among large armada of HE-instruments, within $50 \mu\text{s}$!
Important for multi-messenger signals: GW, FRB, neutrino, GRB, ...
- Studies on total (=PWN+PSR) emission of PSR B1509-58, PSR B0540-69, PSR J1811-1925, PSR J1617-5055, PSR J1846-0258, ...
- Deep wide field imaging: Three new energetic pulsars identified in soft γ -ray sources:
 - IGR J18490-0000
 - IGR J14003-6326
 - IGR J11014-6103
- Contributions to soft γ -ray pulsar catalogue: pulsed fractions!

INTEGRAL Crab pulsar > 300 keV: 2003 - 2021

SPI-SE results, however, spoiled by lower energetic photons due to flaw in AFEE... Avoid >300 keV

Timing in the soft γ -ray band: 20 keV - 30 MeV

Fermi GBM:

12 NaI detectors (8-1000 keV)
2 BGO detectors (0.1-40 MeV)

>300 keV

TTE mode since 26/11/2012: $2\mu\text{s}$; 128 channels

Fermi GBM-BGO Crab pulsar signal build-up across 9 years (Nov-2012 - Dec-2021)

Crab GBM-BGO 0.10–0.75 MeV [0,15]

Crab GBM-BGO 0.75–3.0 MeV [16,50]

Crab GBM-BGO 3.0–30.0 MeV [51,118]

3–30 MeV: 12.0σ

Fermi-LAT Vela
2020-2021

Fermi GBM-NaI Vela
2020/2021/2022a

NICER Vela
2020-2021

Our targets: All located in Scutum region

EXO 1846-031 at (29.958,-0.919) in Outburst Jul. '19

Swift J1845.7-0037 at (31.715,+0.929) in Outburst Oct. '19

AX J1838.0-0655 NICER (Swift) timing

Single structured
broad pulse at X-rays
easy to time

Swift - NICER timing:

MJD 57831-58730
(19/3/17 - 3/9/19)

>>> ToA modelling easy

Glitches	
RXTE era:	1
Gap RXTE/ Swift/NICER	1+
NICER era:	3

AX J1838.0-0655: Fermi GBM NaI & BGO, Fermi-LAT

Pulse phase folding across
March '17 - Nov '21 (4.7 years)

Detection of pulsed emission up
to ~300 keV (NaI)

BGO folding: pulsed emission
up to ~2.5 MeV!

MeV pulsations!

Fermi-LAT 30-1000 MeV:
indication for pulsed emission

IGR J18490-0000: NICER timing (5.07 years)

Single broad pulse at X-rays

Easy to time at X-rays

Very stable rotation since RXTE detection in Nov/Dec 2010:

No Glitches detected yet!

IGR J18490-0000: Fermi GBM NaI / LAT

- Pulse phase folding across period 26/1/17 - 13/4/22
MJD 57779 - 59682 (5.07 years ; 23.7 Ms/ NaI)
- Significant detection of pulsed emission at 100-300 keV!
- GBM NaI: No detection (yet) at > 300 keV
- GBM BGO: Detection in 100-300 keV band
- Fermi-LAT:

No detection at

30-300 MeV

0.3-3 GeV

> 3 GeV

PSR J1846-0258: 2020 Outburst NICER/NuSTAR

Difficult to time: noisy, weak > 7.5 ks / obs.

Pulsed count rate 2.5-10 keV 2020 & 2021

PSR J1846-0258: Second magnetar-like outburst in summer 2020

Rotation behaviour from detection
in 1999 up to Nov, 2021

PSR J2022+3842 - Two sharp X-ray pulses

➤ Very weak radio pulsar PSR J2022+3842 →

NICER X-ray timing (26/11/17 +):
➤ Two large glitches!!

➤ NuSTAR observation at MJD 58134: clear 20-60 keV detection (11 σ)!

➤ Fermi-LAT : Significant detection (9.2 σ) at high-energy γ -rays → Pulses aligned!

Detectable in 30-100 MeV band!

PSR J1813-1246

(Fermi LAT blind pulsar; radio-quiet)

$$P = 48.1 \text{ ms} ; L_{sd} = 6.2E36 \text{ erg/s} ; \tau = 43 \text{ ky}$$

Fermi-LAT gamma-ray (>100 MeV) spectrum:

$$\Gamma = 2.15 \pm 0.02 \quad \leftarrow \text{Very soft}$$

$$E_c = 3.6 \pm 0.3 \text{ GeV}$$

XMM-Newton EPIC-pn Small Window Mode (5.7 ms)

X-ray Spectrum : very hard and highly absorbed:

$$\Gamma = 0.85 \pm 0.03$$

$$N_H = (1.56 \pm 0.07)E22 \text{ cm}^{-2}$$

Pulsed fraction at X-rays : $96 \pm 3\%$!!

X-rays - γ -rays mis-aligned ~ 0.25

Archival RXTE-PCA: Two sharp X-ray pulses

Marelli et al., ApJ 795, 168 (2014)

**GBM NaI 2.6 years: 10.3 σ !
(20-300 keV)**

**No X-ray/ γ -ray misalignment!
(XMM-EPIC pn frame jump..)**

PSR J1813-1246

Fermi-GBM BGO
2020-2022a

Pulsations in MeV band!!
COMPTEL l=18 source?
(l,b)=(17.24,+2.44)

Fermi-GBM NaI 2020-2022a

Fermi-LAT: 2016-2021

Timing six energetic rotation-powered pulsars with NICER, NuSTAR and Chandra

W. Ho, L. Kuiper, C. Espinoza, et al., ApJ in press (2022)

NICER-monitoring yields phase-coherent timing models (ephemerides), $\nu=\nu(t)$, enabling:

- Detailed study of pulse shape at 0.3-10 keV
- Search for pulsed emission at (soft) γ -rays (NuSTAR > 20 keV; Fermi GBM, LAT)
- Identify glitches (neutron star quakes) yielding structure information
- Search for continuous GW-signal using LIGO, Virgo, KAGRA (deformation of ns's)

- Identifying [PSR J1101-6101](#) associated with [IGR J11014-6103](#) as soft γ -ray pulsar in NuSTAR data
- Possibly, 0.3-3 GeV pulsed emission in Fermi LAT data

- [PSR J0058-7218](#) is 21.8 ms RPP in Small Magellanic Cloud SN-remnant IKT 16
- Pulse width: FWHM 3 ms; hard spectrum at X-rays
- Surprisingly, no glitch yet in ~15 months NICER timing (likely one occurring end Aug/early Sept. 2022)
- Possibly, > 500 MeV pulsed emission in Fermi LAT data
- 4x weaker in 20-50 keV than Vela pulsar: difficult for Fermi-GBM NaI, possible for NuSTAR

Summary, conclusions & closing remarks

- Presentation of historical overview of the field, and report on the INTEGRAL contributions
- Update on the soft γ -ray pulsar population using up-to-date timing models acquired mainly by NICER (LAT) monitoring. We discovered pulsed emission at 100-300 keV for AX J1838.0-0655, IGR J18490-0000, PSR J1846-0258, PSR J2022+3842, PSR J1813-1246 [Crab, Vela, PSR B1509-58] and even MeV pulsed emission from two pulsars:

AX J1838.0-0655, PSR J1813-1246

- New member IGR J11014-6103, pulsed emission >20 keV (NuSTAR): 19 secure members
- Potential new member PSR J0058-7218 (IKT 16 pulsar in SMC)
- Perspective: Compton Spectrometer & imager COSI (NASA SMEX 2025/2026; 0.2-5 MeV)

Finally, a dedicated MeV mission...

But, to make further progress more sensitive missions are required covering a larger bandpass 0.1 - 100 MeV e.g. AMEGO, e-ASTROGAM

Geometries of high-energy emission pulsar models

PSR B1509-58 update: CGRO BATSE, RXTE HEXTE & Fermi LAT

Kuiper & Hermsen 2015

PASS8 ; Aug. 2008 -Dec. 2015

PASS7 ; Aug. 2008 -Dec. 2011

Huge improvement!

